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**STUDY OF THE KINETICS OF THE CATALYTIC PURIFICATION
PROCESS OF INDUSTRIAL WASTE AND AUTOMOTIVE EXHAUST
GASES**

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***Abstract.** This article presents the results of studying the kinetics of the catalytic purification process of industrial waste and automobile exhaust gases. As a result of studying the kinetics of the process of reducing nitrogen oxides in nitric acid exhaust gases to ammonia, the reaction order and activation energy value were determined. The obtained data are recommended for use in calculating the design of the experimental reactor.*

***Keywords:** Industrial waste, automobile exhaust, catalysis, kinetics, efficiency.*

Nature is a source of resources necessary for human survival. Only thanks to these three supports, air, water, soil (atmosphere, hydrosphere and lithosphere), humanity can exist forever. There is no doubt that nature will change as a result of human activity.

This change is intensifying as the productive forces develop. Everything in nature is interconnected and in relative balance.

In recent years, these changes have become so widespread and widespread that they threaten to disrupt the existing relative balance in nature. Every year, 120 billion tons of ore are mined in the world. Only 2 percent of it is used. 98 percent is thrown away as waste. 60 million tons of synthetic substances, 100 million tons of mineral fertilizers, and 3 million tons of toxic chemical compounds are produced. All of this pollutes the environment. Environmental pollution poses a great threat to human health and hinders the development of productive forces. That is why environmental protection has become a universal problem.

For the first time, mass illness as a result of air pollution was recorded in Belgium in 1930. In 1952, 4,000 people died from this disease in London. It is enough to say that in European countries and the United States, deaths from chronic bronchitis are doubling every ten years. According to the World Health Organization, three out of every four cancers are associated with environmental pollution. In particular, the increase in chemical mutagens in the environment poses a great danger of the formation of unfavorable mutations in the human body. As a result, the birth of mentally and physically weak babies increases, or in newly formed families, babies are not born, and even at birth they are born with a disease. Currently, in many countries, deaths from congenital diseases are higher than deaths from infectious diseases among children.

The main sources of pollution of the environment with nitrogen oxides are thermal power plants operating on solid, liquid, and gas fuels, motor transport, as well as ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy. Chemical industry enterprises do not emit large amounts of waste into the atmosphere, but due to their proximity to residential areas, they pose a significant threat to the health of the population.

The main way to solve the problem of atmospheric air protection in the chemical industry is to further improve existing production facilities and develop new methods for cleaning exhaust gases from harmful gases.

The process of catalytic reduction of harmful nitrogen oxides contained in nitric acid production waste gases to nitrogen at high temperature is widespread. The purification is carried out under high pressure at a temperature in the range of 673-1073 K at a volumetric flow rate of 20,000 m³/s. In this catalyst, the surface of the aluminum oxide pellets is coated with 2% palladium. Natural gas is used as the reducing agent. The chemical process of this purification can be conditionally imagined by the following reaction example:

The combustion temperature of the catalysts is 673 K for natural gas. The maximum temperature for the catalyst bed in this process is 1088 K. The optimum temperature is 1023-1073 K, for each percent oxygen in the processed gas, the temperature increases by 150-160. Therefore, the amount of reducing agent consumed for the combustion of the catalyst depends on the oxygen in the gas being cleaned. The average cost of gas conversion exceeds the stoichiometric value by 10-30%. The amount of nitrogen oxides removed from exhaust gases depends on the ratio of natural gas to oxygen and temperature. The design load of the APK-2 active contact ensures that the sanitary standards for gas cleaning are met. However, the service life is not long - the warranty is 1 year. This is explained as follows: the catalyst supplied with the reactor operates in different conditions, one third of the catalyst layer interacts with highly toxic contacts. However, the temperature in this zone is 833 K. The last third of the layer (2nd layer) is less affected by poisons. However, a relatively high temperature of 1043 K is recorded. Such variability in the operation of the catalyst layers certainly affects its activity. After 8000 m³/s, the temperature in all layers of the contact decreases and the gas purification decreases from 97.2 to 90.1. Naturally, the mechanical strength of the catalyst changes. After 9000 hours of operation, the first layer becomes unusable by 25.7%. The second layer becomes unusable by 56.4%, and

it is necessary to replace it. Nitric acid production plants are equipped with high-temperature catalytic purification equipment.

The disadvantage of the high-temperature catalytic method is that it is complex to equip, requires the construction of a reactor operating at temperatures above 993 K, and requires the use of expensive catalysts.

The main reason for the high-temperature catalytic method is the use of natural gas as a reducing agent, even when highly active catalysts are used. Therefore, the implementation of a process that allows the purification of exhaust gases from nitrogen oxides at low temperatures is one of the urgent issues.

The catalytic purification process at low temperatures can be carried out in the presence of hydrogen along with natural gas. This simplifies the process equipment, ensures "autothermality of the process" during the start-up of the equipment, and also makes it possible to use catalysts that do not contain precious metals or contain a small amount of precious metals. In this case, catalytic purification is possible when the hydrogen consumption is close to the stoichiometric coefficient (2). The development of a catalytic process that allows for the purification of exhaust gases at lower temperatures on cheaper catalysts, and for this purpose, significantly reducing the consumption of the reducing agent, is of great interest to researchers from both theoretical and practical aspects.

At the same time, while in existing technologies, nitrogen oxides are reduced to nitrogen and released into the atmosphere, this study studied the kinetics of the reduction process of nitrogen oxides to ammonia and its return to the cycle.

In this study, the possibility of reducing the active component of the catalyst was sought in order to reduce the cost of precious metals.

The optimal conditions for the purification of nitric acid production exhaust gases on mixed low-percentage palladium catalysts and the use of hydrogen as a reducing agent for this purpose were studied.

Nitrogen oxides were determined by the method of evacuation of flasks.

To determine the amount of ammonia in the exhaust gas, the gas being analyzed was passed through a container filled with 50% sulfuric acid. Low-percentage palladium catalysts were selected for testing. The activity of catalysts that allow achieving the set goal in laboratory equipment has been studied [1].

It is known that return gas can also be used in catalytic cleaning. Return gas increases the efficiency of cleaning. However, when cleaning large amounts of gases, return gas may not be enough. Therefore, it is advisable to use “tank” gases containing hydrogen together with return gases. This is practically possible only when oil refineries and nitric acid production are close. (Fergana nitrogen fertilizer production and oil refineries). Therefore, it is useful to use a mixture of hydrogen and hydrocarbons (propane-butane mixture) as a reducing gas.

The process of reducing nitrogen oxides in exhaust gases to ammonia was studied in a mixture of exhaust gases and hydrogen on a palladium-manganese-potassium catalyst.

The use of hydrogen gas as a reducing gas allows cleaning to be carried out at low temperatures. In this case, the apparatus is simplified. The autothermal nature of the process is ensured. Also, the catalyst may not contain precious metals. Or it may contain partially precious metals. However, when hydrogen is consumed in a stoichiometric ratio ($H_2/O_2 + NO = 2$), in enterprises where there is no nitrogen-hydrogen addition, nitrogen-hydrogen addition is not used as a reducing agent. This reduces the amount of hydrogen. Also, it is not economically justified. Thus, the study of a highly active Pd –Co- Mn- K/ -Al₂O₃ catalyst with low hydrogen consumption at low temperatures is of practical and theoretical importance.

The tests were carried out on a known device. The experiments were carried out in a stationary bed reactor. The temperature range was from 3730 to 6730K, the volumetric flow rate was 15000 + 30000 m³/s; the ratios N₂/O₂ + NO: from 0.43 to 1.71 and the linear velocity was 0.2 m/s.

The above-mentioned nitrogen oxide removal depends on the temperature, volumetric flow rate and composition of the final exhaust gas mixture. Thermodynamic

calculations of the transformation of nitrogen oxides in two directions were performed to determine the possibilities of the reaction flow. The magnitude of the change in the isobaric-isothermal potential was

1. Table. Logarithmic values of equilibrium constants at different temperatures

	433	453	473	493	513	533	553	573	600
$\text{NO} + 2,5\text{H}_2 = \text{NH}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	37,5	35,45	33,58	31,86	30,27	28,74	27,41	20,14	24,5
$\text{NO} + 5\text{H}_2 = 0,5\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	35,12	32,83	30,72	28,79	27,00	25,94	23,81	22,36	20,5

determined from the Temkin-Schwartzman equation:

$$G_t = \Delta H_{298} - \Delta S_{298}T (\Delta a M_0 + \Delta b M_1 + \Delta c M_2)$$

ΔH_{298} – standard heat of formation of the substances participating in the reaction; kJoule / mol;

ΔS_{298} – standard entropy of the substances participating in the reaction; kJ / mol;

a,b,c- temperature coefficient of heat capacity;

M_0, M_1, M_2 – Temkin-Schwartzman integrals.

The high value of the constant indicates that nitrogen oxides can be completely converted into ammonia and nitrogen molecules.

At temperatures in the range of $4330 \div 6000\text{K}$, the rate constant for the formation of ammonia from nitrogen oxides is significantly higher. Of course, at temperatures of 7000K , the opposite situation is observed. At temperatures below 7000K , the formation of ammonia from nitrogen oxides may decrease. At temperatures above this, the nitrogen molecule becomes the main product [2].

As a result of studying the kinetics of the process of reducing nitrogen oxides contained in nitric acid waste gases to ammonia, the reaction order and activation energy value were determined.

The following scheme of nitrogen oxides reduction with hydrogen was proposed:

According to the proposed scheme, the reduction of nitrogen oxides with hydrogen occurs through adsorbed nitrogen oxides. Which are reduced either to nitrogen or to ammonia. The recombination process at low temperatures can only occur with the participation of nitrogen oxide atoms. The activation energy of the recombination process of nitrogen oxide atoms is 43.1 kJ / mol.

The data obtained were used to calculate the design of the experimental reactor.

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